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Optimizing Real-Time Freshness: Deep Joint Source–Channel Coding Based AoI in Wireless Networks

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Abstract—This paper proposes a deep joint source-channel coding (DJSCC) to minimize the age of information (AoI) for image transmission. A new content-based AoI metric called age of misclassified information (AoMI) is introduced to estimate the freshness of the information in an image classification system. AoMI is a critical metric in timely information delivery, measuring the age of the most recently received and correctly classified image at the receiver. The proposed system leverages a deep neural network at the transmitter to map image pixels directly to channel input symbols, eliminating the need for separate source and channel coding. At the receiver, the channel output is processed to perform image classification. To analyze the AoMI performance of the system, a stochastic hybrid systems (SHS) approach is employed. Closed-form expressions for the average AoMI (AAoMI) are derived, providing insights into the impact of system parameters on the AoMI. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed DJSCC-based system in achieving lower AoMI compared to traditional separate source and channel coding schemes. The findings highlight the potential of deep learning techniques to maintain the freshness of the information in wireless communication systems. This work paves the way for the design of wireless communication systems that prioritize the freshness of delivered information – this is crucial in applications such as real-time monitoring, surveillance, and control systems.

Index Terms—Age of information (AoI), deep joint source and channel coding (DJSCC), semantic communication, deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid growth of wireless devices and applications, there is an increasing demand for freshness of the information over wireless networks. Many emerging applications, such as real-time monitoring, surveillance, and control systems, require fresh information updates to enable swift decision-making and actions [1], [2]. However, traditional timeliness metrics, such as latency, fail to adequately capture and quantify

the freshness of the delivered information. To address this issue, the concept of Age of Information (AoI) has recently been proposed as a performance metric to quantify information freshness in communication systems [3]–[5]. AoI measures the time elapsed since the generation of the latest successfully received update at the destination [6]. Whilst AoI provides valuable insights into the timeliness of information delivery, it does not capture the impact of information content on the usefulness of the delivered data. In many applications, such as image classification in surveillance systems, not all information updates are equally important. The successful delivery of key semantic information is more critical than receiving every single update. Motivated by this observation, this paper proposes a novel performance metric called Age of Misclassified Information (AoMI), which measures the age of the most recently received and correctly classified semantic information at the receiver.

To minimise AoMI in wireless image classification systems, this paper leverages the recent advancements in deep learning and proposes a deep joint source-channel coding (DJSCC) approach. DJSCC utilises a deep neural network (DNN) to map the source signal directly to the channel input, eliminating the need for separate source and channel coding. This approach has shown promising results in improving the efficiency and robustness of wireless communication systems [7].

The main contributions of this paper are as follows: (1) introducing a new performance metric, AoMI, to measure the freshness of correctly classified semantic information in wireless communication systems; (2) proposing a DJSCC-based system that minimizes AoMI by using a DNN at the transmitter to map image pixels directly to channel input symbols and a classifier at the receiver for image classification; (3) developing a stochastic hybrid systems (SHS) approach to analyze the AoMI performance, deriving closed-form expressions for average AoMI (AAoMI); and (4) conducting extensive simulations to evaluate the AoMI of the proposed system and compare it with traditional separate source and channel coding schemes using Better Portable Graphics (BPG) [8] compression and Low-density parity-check (LDPC) coding

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[9].

To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first work that investigates the use of DJSCC for minimising AoI in wireless communication systems. The rest of this paper is organised as follows. Section II describes the system model, the proposed DJSCC-based approach and the AAoMI analysis using SHS. Section III provides the simulation results and discussions. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The study introduces a wireless communication system arrangement consisting of transmitter, channel, and receiver components, as shown in Fig. 1, for image transmission. It is assumed that the source image-capture process adheres to a Poisson point process. The transmitter employs the DJSCC technique for wireless image transmission, mapping image pixel values onto complex-valued channel input symbols. These complex-valued channel input symbols are subsequently transmitted through a wireless communication channel between the source and destination. One of the key aspects of this system model is the joint training of both the transmitter and receiver. This collaborative training strategy enables adaptation to changing channel conditions, ensuring robust image transmission despite the inherently dynamic nature of the channel.

In the considered system, the receiver executes classification tasks utilizing the channel output. The input image is denoted as $\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{I_H \times I_W \times I_C}$, where I_H , I_W , and I_C represent the height, width, and number of color channels, respectively. The total number of pixels in the image is denoted as $k_P = I_H \times I_W \times I_C$, which is referred to as the source bandwidth. The transmitter employs a DNN encoded by the DJSCC encoder, denoted as $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$, where ϑ represents the learnable parameters of the network. Given an input source signal \mathbf{I} , the output encoded semantic features \mathbf{s} produced by $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$ are expressed as $\mathbf{s} = f(\mathbf{I}, \vartheta)$, and \mathbf{s} belongs to the real vector space \mathbb{R}^{2n_T} , where n_T is the channel bandwidth. The ratio " n_T/k_P " is called the bandwidth ratio [10]. The encoded semantic features \mathbf{s} are then reshaped into complex-valued symbols n_T to form the encoded signal $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$. After encoding the semantic signal \mathbf{s} from the images received from the source \mathbf{I} , a normalization step ensures that $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ satisfies the average power constraint as

$$\frac{1}{n_T} \mathbb{E}|\hat{\mathbf{s}}|^2 \leq P, \quad (1)$$

where P denotes the transmission power of the source. Subsequently, the encoded signal $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ is transmitted through the wireless channel between the source and the destination. It is assumed that the channel's characteristics remain stable throughout the transmission of a single symbol; however, they may independently vary when subsequent symbols are transmitted. Consequently, the received signal, represented as $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{C}^{n_T}$, can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{z} = \sqrt{P}\hat{\mathbf{s}} + \mathbf{W}_n, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_n)$ represents independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) circularly symmetric complex Gaussian noise with an average noise power of σ^2 . The average signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is then given by $\gamma = 10 \log_{10} \frac{P}{\sigma^2}$ (dB).

At the receiver end, the real and imaginary components of \mathbf{z} are reshaped to form $\hat{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n_T}$ for further processing. The receiver then performs classification tasks based on $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$. This involves feeding the derived features $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ into a classifier $M(\cdot, \tau)$, where τ denotes the learnable parameters of the network. The classifier outputs the classification result $L = M(\hat{\mathbf{z}}, \tau)$. The performance of the image classification task is evaluated using classification accuracy. The encoder consists of convolutional neural network (CNN) layers, followed by normalization through generalized divisive normalization (GDN) transformations and a parametric rectified linear unit (PReLU) activation function. This architecture is chosen because CNN layers are effective at extracting salient features from images, GDN facilitates local divisive normalization beneficial for density modeling and image compression, and non-linear activations allow learning complex mappings from the source signal space to the channel input space. The classifier model uses dense layers with activation functions sigmoid or ReLU. It is trained using the Adamax optimizer with sparse categorical cross-entropy as the loss function. The final encoder layer has a depth parameter n_{con} , determining the overall bandwidth ratio across all layers as [10]:

$$\frac{n_T}{k_P} = \frac{\left(\frac{I_H}{4} \times \frac{I_W}{4} \times n_{\text{con}}\right)}{I_H \times I_W \times I_C} = \frac{n_{\text{con}}}{16 \times I_C}. \quad (3)$$

A. Estimating the Age of Misclassified Information

This section aims to estimate the AAoMI of the deep learning-based wireless communication system. We assume that the average image generation rate at the transmitter is denoted by λ_I , and the wireless communication system transmits images at a rate of μ . Furthermore, we consider the probability of correct image classification as $0 \leq \rho_{ac} < 1$. The average image transmission rate μ is inversely proportional to the mean transmission time per image, denoted by $\mathbb{E}[T]$, within this wireless network. This relationship is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{\mu} = \mathbb{E}[T] = n_T T_s \quad (4)$$

where T_s represents the symbol duration, and n_T denotes the total number of symbol used for the transmission by the transmitter. If the generation time stamp of the received image with the most recently correctly classified image received at timestamp t is represented by $g(t)$, then AoMI can be defined as a random process as

$$x_0(t) = t - g(t). \quad (5)$$

The illustration in Fig. 2 assumes that AoMI measurements commence at $t = 0$, with the initial AoI at the receiver set as $x_0(0) = X_0$. The source generates images at timestamps

Fig. 1. Proposed DJSCC-based communication system. The transmitter sends images captured by a source, assuming a Poisson point process for image capture. DJSCC technique is used for wireless image transmission. The receiver processes channel output for classification.

$\{c_1, c_2, \dots\}$, while the receiver obtains these images at timestamps $\{w_1, w_2, \dots\}$. As per Fig. 2, for an image i captured at $t = c_i$, the receiver classifies it at $w_i = c_i + n_T T_s$. If correctly classified at w_i , the AoMI at the receiver is estimated as:

$$x(w_i) = n_T T_s. \quad (6)$$

The AoMI of the receiver grows linearly until a correct classification occurs. For instance, if misclassified at w_2 , $x_0(t)$ continues increasing linearly. Moreover, when transmitting an image, newly generated images at the source are blocked and discarded. Specifically, if a new image is captured at c_4 while an earlier image from c_3 is still being transmitted, the c_4 image is not transmitted and does not affect the AoMI process. To calculate the average AoMI over a period T_c , the area under $x_0(t)$ is utilized:

Fig. 2. Evolution of AoMI $x_0(t)$ with the time at the receiver: Source generate images at time stamps c_1, c_2, \dots and the receiver receives and classifies these images at time stamps w_1, w_2, \dots .

$$\Delta_{T_c} = \frac{1}{T_c} \int_0^{T_c} x_0(t) dt. \quad (7)$$

The time-averaged AoMI (Δ_{T_c}) converges to the ensemble average AoMI as $T_c \rightarrow \infty$, expressed as:

$$\Delta = \mathbb{E}[x_0] = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[x_0(t)] = \lim_{T_c \rightarrow \infty} \Delta_{T_c}. \quad (8)$$

This study employs SHS techniques to estimate $\mathbb{E}[x_0]$, representing the AoMI at the receiver. Within the SHS framework, the AoMI process is modeled by combining continuous states $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and discrete states $q(t)$. These discrete states signify the wireless system's transmission status, effectively described by a Markov chain. The state space is defined as $(q(t), \mathbf{x}(t))$, where $q(t) \in \mathcal{Q} = \{0, 1\}$; $q = 0$ indicates an idle system, while $q = 1$ signifies active transmission. The continuous vector $\mathbf{x}(t) = [x_1(t), x_0(t)]$ evaluates the age process, where $x_0(t)$ monitors the age for correctly classified images, and $x_1(t)$ represents the projected $x_0(t)$ value for accurate classification. The AoMI process is visually represented as a graph $(\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{L})$, with transmission states as nodes and transitions as directed edges. The transition rate from node q_l to q'_l is given by $\lambda^{(l)} \delta_{q_l, q'_l}$, where the Kronecker delta δ_{q_l, q'_l} ensures transitions occur only for state q_l . Each transition l corresponds to a sudden change in the continuous state, represented by a linear transition reset mapping:

$$\mathbf{x}' = \mathbf{x} \mathbf{A}_l, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_l \in \{0, 1\}^{(2) \times (2)}$ is a binary transition reset matrix. For this system, the interactions between discrete states and their impact on continuous states are summarized in Table I through linear mapping. The transactions described in Table I can be interpreted as follows: (1) When the wireless system is idle, an image is generated by the source. The system starts transmitting the captured image, but $x'_0 = x_0$ remains

unchanged since image capture does not reduce the age at the receiver until correct classification. However, $x'_1 = 0$ since the age of the captured image is initially zero. (2) When the receiver correctly classifies an image transmitted by the source, $x'_0 = x_1$, resetting the age at the receiver to the age of the transmitted image. Moreover, $x'_1 = 0$ since x_1 becomes irrelevant when the source system enters the idle state 0. (3) In the case of the receiver misclassifying an image transmitted by the source, $x'_0 = x_0$ remains unchanged since misclassification does not reduce the age at the receiver. Additionally, $x'_1 = 0$ since x_1 becomes irrelevant when the system enters state 0. (4) If the source captures an image while another image is being transmitted, the new image is discarded, and transmission continues with the current image. In this scenario, $x'_0 = x_0$ remains unchanged since this operation does not affect the age at the receiver. Furthermore, $x'_1 = x_1$ is unaffected since the age of the transmitting image remains unchanged. The growth rate of the continuous state at each discrete $q(t) = q$, where $q \in \mathcal{Q}$, is given by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}(t)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{b}_q, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_q = [\mathbf{b}_{q,0}, \mathbf{b}_{q,1}]$ is a vector containing binary elements. When $\mathbf{x}_j(t)$ grows at a unit rate as a normal age process in state q , $\mathbf{b}_{q,j} = 1$; and when it is irrelevant to the age process or not tracked in state q , $\mathbf{b}_{q,j} = 0$. Hence, for this system, \mathbf{b}_q can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{b}_q = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, & q = 0, \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & q = 1. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Let $\pi_{\hat{q}}(t)$ denote the discrete state probabilities for all $\hat{q} \in \mathcal{Q}$, and $\mathbf{v}_{\hat{q}}(t)$ denote the correlation between the age process and the discrete state $q(t) = \hat{q}$. Accordingly, we have $\pi_{\hat{q}}(t) = \mathbb{E}[\delta_{\hat{q},q(t)}]$, and the correlation vector function $\mathbf{v}_{\hat{q}}(t) = [v_{\hat{q}0}(t), v_{\hat{q}1}(t)]$, where $v_{\hat{q}j}(t) = \mathbb{E}[x_j(t)\delta_{\hat{q},q(t)}]$, $j \in (0, 1)$. All transitions \mathcal{L} can be divided into incoming and outgoing transitions. For each state q , incoming transitions are labeled as $\mathcal{L}'_q = \{l \in \mathcal{L} : q'_l = q\}$, and outgoing transitions are labeled as $\mathcal{L}_q = \{l \in \mathcal{L} : q_l = q\}$. To compute the time-averaged age, it is assumed that the Markov chain $q(t)$ is ergodic. Hence, the state probability vector $\pi(t) = [\pi_0(t), \pi_1(t)]$ converges to a unique stationary vector $\bar{\pi} = [\bar{\pi}_0, \bar{\pi}_1]$ satisfying the following:

$$\bar{\pi}_{\bar{q}} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}'_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)} = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}'_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)} \bar{\pi}_{q_l}, \quad \bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}, \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{\bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}} \bar{\pi}_{\bar{q}} = 1. \quad (13)$$

For this system, (12) has been used to find the stationary probabilities, and it can be shown that the stationary probability vector satisfies $\bar{\pi} \mathbf{A} = \bar{\pi} \mathbf{B}$, where:

$$\mathbf{A} = \text{diag} [\lambda_I \quad \mu + \lambda_I], \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \lambda_I \\ \mu & \lambda_I \end{bmatrix}.$$

TABLE I
TRANSITIONS RATE FOR THE MARKOV CHAIN.

l	$q_l \rightarrow q'_l$	$\lambda^{(l)}$	$\mathbf{x} \mathbf{A}_l$	$\mathbf{v}_{q_l} \mathbf{A}_l$
1	0 \rightarrow 1	λ_I	$\begin{bmatrix} x_0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v_{00} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
2	1 \rightarrow 0	$\mu \rho_{ac}$	$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v_{11} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
3	1 \rightarrow 0	$\mu(1 - \rho_{ac})$	$\begin{bmatrix} x_0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v_{10} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
4	1 \rightarrow 1	λ_I	$\begin{bmatrix} x_0 & x_1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} v_{10} & v_{11} \end{bmatrix}$

Applying (13), the stationary probabilities can be calculated as

$$\bar{\pi} = [\bar{\pi}_0 \quad \bar{\pi}_1] = \frac{1}{\lambda_I + \mu} [\mu \quad \lambda_I]. \quad (14)$$

When $\pi(t) = \bar{\pi}$ and $\mathbf{v}(t) = [\mathbf{v}_0(t), \mathbf{v}_1(t)]$, the system follows first-order differential equations for all $\bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}$ as

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}_{\bar{q}}(t) = \mathbf{b}_{\bar{q}} \bar{\pi}_{\bar{q}} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}'_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)} \mathbf{v}_{q_l}(t) \mathbf{A}_l - \mathbf{v}_{\bar{q}}(t) \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)}, \quad (15)$$

Under the ergodicity assumption, this differential equation is stable, and $\mathbf{v}_{\bar{q}}(t) = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}(t)\delta_{\bar{q},q(t)}]$ converges to a non-negative limit $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{\bar{q}}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Accordingly:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}] = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}(t)] = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}(t)\delta_{\bar{q},q(t)}] = \sum_{\bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}} \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{\bar{q}}, \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{\bar{q}} \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)} = \mathbf{b}_{\bar{q}} \bar{\pi}_{\bar{q}} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}'_{\bar{q}}} \lambda^{(l)} \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{q_l} \mathbf{A}_l, \quad \bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}, \quad (17)$$

Here, $x_0(t)$ is the age at the destination, and the AAOmI is calculated as:

$$\Delta = \mathbb{E}[x_0] = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[x_0(t)] = \sum_{\bar{q} \in \mathcal{Q}} \bar{v}_{\bar{q}0}. \quad (18)$$

To estimate AAOmI using (18), it is necessary to find $\bar{v}_{\bar{q}0}$ from (17). First, a solution for $\bar{\mathbf{v}} = [\bar{\mathbf{v}}_0, \bar{\mathbf{v}}_1] = [\bar{v}_{00}, \bar{v}_{01}, \bar{v}_{10}, \bar{v}_{11}]$ can be found using (17). Evaluating this equation at $q = 0$ and $q = 1$, and using Table I, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_I [\bar{v}_{00} \quad \bar{v}_{01}] &= [\bar{\pi}_0 \quad 0] + \mu \rho_{ac} [\bar{v}_{11} \quad 0] \\ &\quad + \mu(1 - \rho_{ac}) [\bar{v}_{10} \quad 0] \quad (19) \\ (\mu + \lambda_I) [\bar{v}_{10} \quad \bar{v}_{11}] &= [\bar{\pi}_1 \quad \bar{\pi}_1] + \lambda_I [\bar{v}_{00} \quad 0] + \lambda_I [\bar{v}_{10} \quad \bar{v}_{11}]. \quad (20) \end{aligned}$$

Then, the above expressions can be written as the following system of equations:

$$\lambda_I \bar{v}_{00} = \bar{\pi}_0 + \mu \rho_{ac} \bar{v}_{11} + \mu(1 - \rho_{ac}) \bar{v}_{10}, \quad (21)$$

$$\mu \bar{v}_{10} = \bar{\pi}_1 + \lambda_I \bar{v}_{00}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mu \bar{v}_{11} = \bar{\pi}_1. \quad (23)$$

By solving these equations and using (14), the values of $\bar{v}_{\bar{q}0}$ can be calculated. Then, by substituting the result into (18), the AAOmI at the destination can be obtained as follows:

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{\lambda_I \rho_{ac}} + \frac{1}{\mu \rho_{ac}} + \frac{\lambda_I}{\mu(\lambda_I + \mu)}. \quad (24)$$

Finally, the AAoMI of the wireless communication system is calculated using Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for Train DJSCC and Calculating AAoMI

Training Phase

- 1: **Require:**A batch of images I for training from the CIFAR-10 [11] image dataset.
- 2: **Ensure:**Trained encoder $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$ and classifier $M(\cdot, \tau)$.
- 3: **Initialize:** Initialize the weights of $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$ and $M(\cdot, \tau)$ using a standard initialisation method.
- 4: **for** each epoch **do**

Transmitter:

- 5: Extract semantic features using $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$.
- 6: Apply power normalisation as in (1).
- 7: Set the wireless channel average SNR as γ_{train} and transmit the symbols through wireless channels.

Receiver:

- 8: Perform reshaping on the received signal z .
- 9: Conduct image classification with $M(\hat{z}, \tau)$.

10: **end for**

Deployment and AAoMI Calculation Phase

- 11: **Require:**A batch of images I_{test} for testing from the CIFAR-10 image dataset.
- 12: **Ensure:**Calculate AAoMI.
- 13: **Initialize:** Image generation process parameters λ_I and image transmission rate μ .

Transmitter:

- 14: Deploy the learned $f(\cdot, \vartheta)$. Extract semantic features s .
- 15: Apply power normalisation as in (1).
- 16: Set the wireless channel parameters. Then, the symbols are transmitted through the wireless channel.

Receiver:

- 17: Perform reshaping on the received signal z and deploy the learned $M(\cdot, \tau)$.
- 18: Conduct image classification using $M(\hat{z}, \tau)$.
- 19: **Compute Classification Accuracy:**
- 20: Compare the predicted class L with the true class of I_{test} .

- 21: Calculate the classification accuracy ρ_{ac} .
- 22: **Compute AAoMI:**
- 23: Calculate AAoMI using

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{\lambda_I \rho_{ac}} + \frac{1}{\mu \rho_{ac}} + \frac{\lambda_I}{\mu(\lambda_I + \mu)}.$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The DJSCC is evaluated using the CIFAR-10 [11] image dataset, which consists of 60,000 32x32 color images, divided into 50,000 training images and 10,000 test images. The training data is combined with random channel realizations to train the DJSCC model. The model is trained using a fixed SNR, and its performance is investigated over a range of SNR values and bandwidth ratios. The proposed DJSCC is

compared with a separate source and channel coding scheme that uses the BPG compression algorithm for source coding and the LDPC code for channel coding as the digital baseline. In this scheme, the source node compresses the image using BPG, which employs advanced coding techniques such as intra-frame prediction and context-adaptive binary arithmetic coding. The BPG encoder uses a quality parameter (QP) to control the trade-off between compression ratio and image quality, determined by a rate-distortion optimization algorithm. The compressed bitstream is encoded using an LDPC code compliant with the 5G New Radio (NR) standard [12]. The LDPC encoder performs rate-matching, including puncturing and shortening, to achieve the desired codeword length. At the receiver, the LDPC decoder employs the iterative belief propagation (BP) decoding algorithm. The decoded bitstream is decompressed using the BPG decompression algorithm to obtain the reconstructed image. In the traditional model, these reconstructed images will be used for a classification task which is trained using the original images, compared to the DJSCC approach. The flexibility and configurability of both the BPG compression algorithm and the LDPC code and decoder provide a strong baseline for comparison with the DJSCC approach. Unless otherwise specified, the simulation parameters are configured as follows: $T_s = 20 \mu\text{s}$, $n_{con} = 16$, $n_T/k_p = 1/3$ and $\frac{\lambda_I}{\mu} = 1$.

Fig. 3. AAoMI vs. channel SNR for different bandwidth ratios (BR).

In Fig. 3, the relationship between AAoMI and channel SNR for different bandwidth ratios is illustrated. In this simulation, the DJSCC models were trained at a fixed SNR of $\gamma_{\text{train}} = 5$ dB, and subsequently, the AAoMI was evaluated across a range of channel SNRs. The AAoMI of the DJSCC-based approach is compared with that of a digital baseline, considering various bandwidth ratios. The digital baseline system, consisting of LDPC + BPG, adapts its compression ratio based on the specified code rate and overall bandwidth ratio. The (3072, 4608) LDPC code, corresponding to a 2/3 code rate, and 4-QAM modulation were evaluated as the digital baseline. The experimental results reveal that the DJSCC approach

exhibits superior AoI performance compared to the digital baseline transmission schemes in low channel bandwidth and low SNR scenarios. Conversely, in high bandwidth ratios and high SNR environments, the traditional system performs better. Importantly, the DJSCC approach does not suffer from the 'cliff effect' commonly observed in digital transmission schemes. This limitation of digital schemes stems from the fact that once the channel code and modulation scheme are chosen for a specific target SNR, the number of bits available for compression remains constant. Consequently, the AAoMI does not improve even when the SNR increases. In addition, when channel quality deteriorates below the target SNR, the channel code struggles to handle the escalating error rate, resulting in a substantial increase in AAoMI at very low SNR levels. On the other hand, for traditional systems, lower SNR and lower bandwidth ratios lead to a higher AAoMI compared with the DJSCC system. This is because the reduction in image quality, caused by high compression levels at lower bandwidth ratios, reduces classification accuracy, especially under lower SNR levels, as the traditional system classifies images at the receiver using a model that is not trained to adapt to the reduction of image quality due to noise or high compression levels. In addition, for both DJSCC-based systems and traditional systems, when the bandwidth ratio is reduced, the AAoMI also reduces since the reduction in transmission time becomes more prominent compared to the reduction in classification accuracy. This adaptability and resilience exhibited by the DJSCC scheme make it an attractive solution for efficient communication in low SNR channel environments, offering potential for improved freshness performance and robustness compared to traditional approaches. Moreover, while the AoI performance of the DJSCC system falls behind traditional schemes in high SNR conditions, it is suggested that adopting a more complex neural network structure and leveraging advanced activation and loss functions could lead to enhancements in the freshness capabilities of the DJSCC model. Fig. 4 presents the inverse

Fig. 4. Comparison of AAoMI against image generation (capturing) rate (λ_I) for different bandwidth ratios (BR).

relationship between the AAoMI and the image generation rate (λ_I) in the evaluated wireless communication system. As the figure illustrates, there is a notable decline in AAoMI with an upsurge in the image capture rate. This system is characterized by the absence of a transmission queue, thus eliminating any queuing delay. The enhanced image capture rate correlates with a more frequent update of images at the destination node. Thus, the decrease in AAoMI can be directly attributed to the increase in temporal density of the image updates received by the receiver, which emphasizes the efficiency of the system in maintaining the freshness of the information.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a novel wireless communication system that employs DJSCC to minimise the AoMI for image transmission. The proposed system leverages a deep neural network at the transmitter and a classifier at the receiver to enable end-to-end optimization of the age of information. By introducing AoMI as a new metric, this work captures the freshness of correctly classified semantic information – this is crucial for time-critical wireless applications that rely on timely delivery of information. Simulations confirmed that the proposed DJSCC system significantly reduces the AoMI compared to traditional schemes. These results underscore the capability of deep learning techniques to enhance the timeliness of information delivery over wireless channels, especially in environments characterized by limited bandwidth and low SNR.

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